

THE MINARETS OF THE HILĀL KHĀN QĀZI MOSQUE, DHOLKĀ

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The medieval Gurjaradeśa,—Gujarāt of our own times,—was the province where Islām entered at an earlier date, in fact much prior to the Muslim conquest of 1298. Islām's advent in Gujarāt, at that early date, was peaceful it would seem. The sacred buildings of Islām in India, earlier than those in Delhi and Ajmer, were, as a result, built on the soil of Gujarāt.¹ The Sadre-e-avval or Jāmi Mosque in Cambay² was founded before the twelfth century and is traditionally held of a date as old as the late eighth century.³ A generation after Maḥmūd of Gazanā's invasion on Somanātha (1026), a mosque, as a contemporary inscriptional evidence is there, was founded in Āśāpalli⁴ in 1053.⁵ One other early mosque is said to have been built in Broach⁶ in about 1066.⁷

Posterior in date to Delhi buildings but still in pre-conquest period are the two mosques, one founded in Prabhāsa-Pāṭaṅ⁸ in 1264,⁹ and the other near Junāgaḍh in 1286-87,¹⁰ in the Saurāṣṭra sector of the province. And as the later Jaina sources mention, Vastupāla, the Prime Minister of the Vāghelā Regent Viradhavala, who was in the ministerial office between 1220 and 1235, had built *masitis* i.e., *masjids* for the benefit of the Muslim populace.¹¹ In the *Jagaḍucarita*,—a biography of the illustrious Jaina tradesman Jagaḍu Śā of Bhadreśvara (in Kutch) written by Sarvānanda Sūri in the latter half of the thirteenth century,—it is stated that Jagaḍu Śā founded a *masiti* (very probably) in Bhadreśvara.¹²

The recent discovery of a fragmentary passage in the *vastuśāstra Jāyapucchā*—a Sanskrit work on the medieval Māru-Gurjara (i.e., Western Indian) civilian architecture (ca. first half of the twelfth century)—concerning the constructional principles of *Rahamāna prāsāda* meaning 'temple of

¹In the context of the pre-partitioned India, Islām of course first entered in Sind in early eighth century through a military conquest and was established there since then.

²The Mosque no more exists. Cambay was known as Stambhatirtha or Khambhāyat in the mediaeval period and at present Khambhāt.

³It was burnt down in a riot in early twelfth century and was soon rebuilt through the munificence of the Solāṅkī king Jayasīnha Siddharāja (1095-1144) of Aṅhilapāṭaka. It was once more rebuilt in 1218: (vide *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic & Persian Supplement pt. 1, 1961, pp. 4-5.)

⁴Renamed Ahmedābād in 1412 by Sultān Aḥmedshāh.

⁵Cf. M. A. Chagtai, "The Earliest Muslim Inscription in India from Ahmedabad", *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, Vol. III, 1939, p. 647.

⁶Anc. Bhrgukaccha.

⁷Vide Imamuddin Dargahwala, "Gujarat-māñ āvelā ārambhika Muslim pracārako" (Gujarātī), *Vallabhavidyānagara Saṁśodhana-patrikā*, Vallabhvidyanagar, Vol. I, No. 2, p. 62.

⁸Anc. Śrī Devapattana.

⁹Cf. D. C. Sircar, "Veraval Inscription of Chaulukya-Vaghela Arjuna, 1264 A.D.", *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. XXXIV, part IV, pp. 141-151.

¹⁰*Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian. Supplement, 1961, 18, pl. V(a).

¹¹Cf. *Purātana-Prabandha-Saṅgraha*: Ed. Shri Jinavijaya Muni, Singhi Jaina Granthamālā, Calcutta 1936. The particular 'manuscript (B)' in the compilation is datable to the 15th century. It gives an exaggerated inventory of Vastupāla's religious foundations and relevant matters, wherein he is credited to have built 84 *masitis*: (cf. p. 65). Vastupāla probably founded mosques at Cambay, Dholkā, and Pāṭaṅ, or at least in one of the three cities.

¹²The mosque has survived. It is, like the Junāgaḍh mosque, rectangular on plan, with two rows of pillars. The doorframe at the entrance is of *ekasākhā*, single-jamb variety with scroll decoration as in temple doorframes, with the notable omission of figural work at the bottom and substitution, instead, by schematic floral motif. The *quibla* does not bear the pointed arch; it is a vaulted cavity. This is not a true arch.

Rahmān' (i.e., mosque),¹³ proves that the buildings sacred to Islām were in that age built in number and size that compelled a Brahmanical work on architecture to take mosque's cognizance. All the earlier Gujarātī mosques, excepting the Bhadrēśvara and the Junāgaḍh one, have disappeared and the nature of these buildings we shall perhaps never know.

From among the post-conquest mosques, the earliest and the largest one, namely, the Adinā Mosque at Pāṭaṅ¹⁴ (1305), was destroyed in the eighteenth century during Marāṭhā occupation. The two buildings next in date and importance, namely, the Jāmi Masjdīd at Cambay (1325) and the Hilāl Khān Qāzi's Masjdīd at Dhoḷkā¹⁵ still survive and are in tolerably good condition. Of the two, the Cambay mosque is more impressive by virtue of its scale: The Dhoḷkā one, though somewhat smaller, is more graceful. What is more, it contains, unlike the former building, only (and rather doubtful) traces of material pilfered from the Brahmanical and Jaina temples earlier desecrated in that town. It is, therefore, a building with a greater emphasis on the pureness of the local Islāmic style of Gujarāt.

The Dhoḷkā Mosque, as a whole, is very chaste in workmanship and possesses several elements—the entrance hall and the grilles in the women's gallery—which are of considerable beauty. Outshining in significance, no less in elegance, is a pair of minarets placed above the marlonned parapet over the central arch of the *maqsura* which screens the prayer hall: (Pl. III).

The *Jayaprīchā* takes no notice of *manār* in the context of mosque, nor do the Bhadrēśvara and the Junāgaḍh mosques referred to earlier have any. It is not certain whether the Gujarāt mosques of the Solāṅkī period (942-1298) possessed minarets. Even when they occur, as they do in Cambay and Dhoḷkā, they are by far small and not particularly monumental as the later ones of the Sultanate period (1412-1537) in Aḥmedābād are. The Cambay ones lack even the primary beauty of shape, besides dimensions.¹⁶

Jas. Burgess was perhaps the first archaeologist to write about this Dhoḷkā mosque¹⁷ with a photographic illustration of its inner front¹⁸ and a drawing along the longitudinal section.¹⁹ Burgess takes only a brief notice of the pair of minarets there: "There are no minārs proper, but two little turrets stand on the front wall,—and on each side of the central arch,—which are quite unlike any other employed in similar circumstances elsewhere: they just stand behind the battlementing of the façade, and are 17 feet high with shafts 2' 3" in diameter."²⁰ (Burgess also gives a small, separate drawing of one of the two minarets.²¹)

While comparing this Hilāl khān Qāzi's mosque with the Cambay one, Percy Brown specially dwelt on its minarets and his comments are more than casual.²² He wrote: "It is a smaller and even simpler structure but with notable innovation to the façade in the shape of a pair of tall ornamental turrets, one on each side of the central archway. In design

¹³See my article in Gujarātī entitled "Māru-Gurjara Vāstuśāstro-māñ Masjdīd-vidhi", *Svādhyāya*, Vol. 7, No. 1, Baroda, V. S. 2025, pp. 64-79.

¹⁴Cf. Jas. Burgess and Henry Cousins, *Architectural Antiquities of Northern Gujarat*, London 1903, ASIR (NIS), Vol. XXXV, p. 30; Pāṭaṅ was known as Aṅhillapāṭaka.

¹⁵*Anc. Dhavalakakka*. The date of the mosque is 1333.

¹⁶Cf. Jas. Burgess. *On the Muhammadan Architecture of Broach, Cambay, Dhoḷka, Champanir, and Mahamudabad in Gujarat*, ASIWI, Vol. VI, London 1896, plate XVII; and Percy Brown, *Indian Architecture (Islamic Architecture)*, Fourth Edition, Bombay 1964, plate XXXIII, fig. 1.

¹⁷*Ibid.*

¹⁸*Ibid.*, pl. XXV.

¹⁹*Ibid.*, pl. XXVII.

²⁰*Ibid.*, p. 22.

²¹*Ibid.*, pl. XXVII.

²²His, unlike Burgess's, is a sort of *discussion*, albeit with no allusion to details.

these turrets are indigenous, with no definite traces of Islamic influence, but they are apparently an attempt to produce something corresponding to a minaret without, however, any exact knowledge as to what this was like, or for what purpose it was intended."²³

Burgess saw these minarets not as "minār proper" but rather as "turrets" which in a certain sense they are, but in a more specific sense they are not; for they really represent *manār* and the builders, despite Brown's assertion to the contrary, certainly knew the purpose for which they were made. The *manār*, like *mihrāb* (and hence the pointed Sarasenic arch) had come, in India, to acquire a special significance, of a religious cognizance of Islām. That must have been soon after the famous Qutb-minār at Delhi built in the year 1200. It thus transcended the purely functional purpose, of the *ādhāna* call summoning the faithful, as it had eventually come to be in the homeland of Islām. The minarets here proceed above *maqsura*'s central arch served the purpose symbolic rather than functional. That is how, in the Indian context, they first occur over the *maqsura* in the old mosque at Ajmer (ca. 1206) where they otherwise seem to follow Qutb-minār's design.²⁴ In Gujarat, too, eight years earlier than the Dholkā example, the great mosque at Cambay shows a pair of minarets in an identical situation.²⁵ Dholkā, just as Cambay examples, are not minaret proper in the sense that minārs or minarets are normally tall, monumental, and oftener functional, starting from over the mosque's base and rising skyward far above the mosque's walling. But they are for certain minarets, symbolically conceived and placed for denoting the distinctive sacred mansion of Islām, *masjid*.

We may next take up Brown's other observations on these minarets. Like Burgess, Brown also calls them 'turrets' and their presence seems to him as a "notable innovation to the façade". But, as I pointed out earlier, the Cambay mosque already shows this feature, and, a century and quarter earlier, the Ajmer mosque shows this innovation in relation to its *maqsura* screen standing in front of and apart from the Ibādatkhānā. There is no question of *innovation*, therefore, on the part of the architect of the Dholkā mosque who just seems to follow the convention previously formalized in Delhi and which must have been known and observed in Gujarāt in his own times.

Brown's second observation, that "In design these turrets are indigenous, with no definite traces of Islamic influence, but they are apparently an attempt to produce something corresponding to a minaret without, however, any exact knowledge as to what this was like. . . ." does not seem valid if we take into account the facts as they are now known about the *manār* in general, some more facts revealed by the minarets themselves, at Dholkā. First, the Dholkā minarets do follow the general pattern of a minaret: The *manār*'s basic conception is clearly reflected in them. As one beholds them, he instinctively knows that they *are* minarets. Their form encourages this belief and their position strengthens it. Second, there is no single standardized shape for *manār*. Many variations developed even in the Middle East, the home of Islām. We have the Syrian, the Irāqi, the Palestinian, the Anatolian, the Armenian, the Egyptian, the Turk, the Afghān and the Irānian varieties, each rooted in and using the architectural elements characteristic of the earlier, very ancient native civilizations that flourished in those lands. In India, too, the minār, after its first introduction, took to

²³Brown, p. 49.

²⁴Cf. Derek Hill and Oleg Crabar, *Islamic Architecture and its Decoration*, London 1964, figs. 524 and 527; also Brown, pl. V, figs. 1 and 2 and pl. VI, fig. 1.

²⁵Cf. Burgess, *On the Muhammadan Architecture.*, pl. XVII; and Brown, pl. XXXIII, fig. 1.

many and varied shapes, each growing from the earlier provincial styles of Hindu architecture. The Gujarāt variety is only one such manifestation and like any other, uses certain native elements, those of the sacred architecture of the Hindus in its formal make up. But the overall form, for certain, is quite non-Hindu: It is very definitely Islāmic. Without the knowledge of the conception of *manār*, a minaret cannot be built. There was a strong Islāmic tradition behind the DhoĪkā minaret even when it presses Hindu elements into service.

Let us, then, analyze its components and see what the results have to indicate. We shall, for the purpose of description, use the terminology of the Māru-Gurjara brahmanical architecture whose elements have gone into its make up.

As the drawing reveals (Text fig. 1), the minaret in question can be resolved from base to the finial into eight components, namely, the *bhīṭṭas* (plinths: two courses), the *piṭha* (base), the first *bhūmi* (1st floor), the *prahāra* (sur-entablature), the second *bhūmi* (2nd floor); the third *bhūmi*, the miniature *manār*, and finally the *kalāśa* (pitcher-finial).

The *piṭha* comprises three mouldings, namely, the *jādyakumbha* (inverted cyma recta), the *antarapaṭṭa* (astragal), and the *chādyaki* (rooflet). The *piṭha* follows the formal organization of Hindu architecture. Next comes the *stambha* or shaft proper divided into three *janṅhā*-sections with the help of *madhyabandha* (medial band) and *kapotāli* (cyma-cornice). Then comes the *kanṭha*, necking, and next the *khuracchādyā*, cyma-awning, of the entablature supported by *madalas*, consoles or strut-brackets. The lower rim of the *khuracchādyā* shows a row of *sārilambanas*, knob-pendants.

There ends the first storey and the next one begins with the *prahāra* made up of *antarapaṭṭa*, deep fillet, and *kapotāli*, cyma-cornice. In the second *bhūmi* proper, the *janṅhā* has been omitted to ensure reduction of height, and in mouldings what we get are only the *antarapaṭṭa* and the *kanṭha* with, as before, *madala*-brackets supporting the cyma-awning. The third storey is further diminished in height, formed as it is by a *cippikā*, minor inverted cyma recta (with sawedge ornament on the astragal), and the *antarapaṭṭa* followed by a small *khuracchādyā* merging at its top with a miniature *manār*, the latter shaped like a cooling tower of an electrical power generating station. The *manār* motif pierces through an unribbed *āmalasāraka*, myrobalan member of the Hindu temple. At *manār*'s top is the *candrikā*, moon-cap, with suspended leaf decoration at its border. And finally the *kalāśa*, pitcher finial, formed by a *ghaṭa* or pitcher proper (also called *aṇḍa*, egg) and the *bijapuraka*, citron fruit, the last one rendered schematically as in the instances of the Māru-Gurjara temples of Gujarāt.

Now to the analysis of the minaret's constituent elements. The minaret's organization upto the end of the first storey more or less follows the conventions of the sacred architecture of the Hindus. The *bhīṭṭas* and the *piṭha* for example, are where they should be in a Hindu structure. The three *janṅhā* registers collectively forming the shaft have a sort of flutings, a feature not found in the Hindu architecture and whose significance we will enlarge upon soon. The *madalas* supporting the *khuracchādyā* of the entablature is a feature rather of the fifteenth century temples than of the earlier ones, but the elements as such were earlier known, in a different context though.²⁶

²⁶The *madalas* are found in the well section of some *vāpīs*; Examples: Harṣā and Pipād (ca. late 9th century) and Vasantagaḍh (ca. late 10th century)—all in Rājasthāna, and Modherā (ca. 1000) and Pāṭaṇ (Ranivāv; ca. 3rd quarter of the 11th century), both in Gujarāt, and, in the *torāṇa* ornamenting the *pratolīs* (gateways) of the forts such as at Jinjhuvādā (ca. 2nd quarter of the 12th century) and Dabhoi (ca. 1225-1253), once again in Gujarāt. A Mālava example is furnished by a gateway at the river at Oṃkāra-Māndhātā: (ca. late 11th century).

The *prahāra*, too, is a component to be found in an identical position in Western Indian Hindu temples. Minaret's second storey, too, corresponds to the second storey encountered in larger temples, though the mouldings used here differ from those in the Hindu temples and the storey concept is only symbolic, not functional. The third storey is smaller, further constricted and reduced in height, consisting as it is of only two elements, the *antara-patta* and the minor *khuracchādyā*. At the finishing point the architect is faced with a problem: He knows what the elements of the crowning part in a Hindu sacred building are, and which must follow suit in view of his using Hindu architectural forms; and yet he has to make it clear that the structure he wants to design is Islāmic. To resolve, therefore, this dilemma, he places a miniature replica of the conventional *manār* and grafts the customary *āmalasāraka* of the Hindu temple with the *manār* and ends with *kalāśa*, the sacred pitcher-finial of the Hindu buildings, for finial no better than that can be conceived in the Indian context.

The Hindu elements, though freely used (and in an orderly fashion to be sure) in these minarets, do not result in a structure that is Hindu either in semblance or feeling. The secret of this phenomenon may be sought in the combination of three factors, each serving the other in the realization of the same objective. First, the over all circular plan and elevation, rather unknown in this manner in Hindu architecture: The medieval Hindu architecture mainly employed parallelepipeds and cubes²⁷ and the major curved masses, organic more than geometric, come in the superstructural part. Second, the condensation of mass resulting in a slenderness in these minarets, of the kind unknown in the Hindu monumental architecture, whether functional, or symbolic. Third, the Hindu elements, though profusely present, are conceptually subordinated to the Islāmic proper in that what actually dominates and ultimately determines the character is in this case the shaft with its prominent flutings. This is a sort quite foreign to Indian wall surfaces, and its place of origin is, as we shall have seen, not India.

The minaret's shaft creates an illusion of an Ionic or a Corinthian column; but the flutings here are triangular in section with blunt tops and from a closer quarter differences in minutiae between this and the typical Corinthian become more obvious. Where, then, do we meet with such a shaft treatment? The Ajmer minarets (and for that matter the Quṭb which they copy) differ from the Dholkā instance in three respects: First, the batter: Second, they are not provided with a base:²⁸ Third, there are no real flutings but what is encountered there is stellate corners (*pallavis*) alternating with the rounded corners (*ṛitta-karṇas*). There is no parallel in India, even in the Islāmic context for the shafts such as of the Dholkā mosque. Not only that: Even in the Middle East, it is very rare: I came across only one parallel with which to compare. That is met at the Great Mosque of Wāsiṭ in Irāq, in the column-drums of its earliest building period datable to A.D. 702-5.²⁹ The drums clearly show flutings somewhat analogous to those of the Dholkā minarets: (cf. here text fig. 2 and pl. 2).

The distance between Wāsiṭ and Dholkā is enormous in terms of space

²⁷The temple base, though cut-up by mouldings, is, in principle, a parallelepiped, and the walls, cube. The Dholkā minarets are cylindrical.

²⁸This feature ultimately derives from the Susan and Ekbatana variety of the Achalmanian column from which the Mauryan columns drew.

²⁹Cf. K.A.C. Creswell, *Early Muslim Architecture*, Vol. I, Part I, Oxford 1969, pp. 131-134 and pl. 39c and d. It is claimed to be the "oldest mosque in Islam of which remains have come down to us." (cf. Creswell, *A Short Account of Early Muslim Architecture*, pt. 1, Victoria 1958, p. 42.)

but also of time: Over two thousand miles, and six centuries separate them. The connection, if not with Wāsiṭ proper, with Middle East is surely there, difficult though it certainly is to work out the links and trace the channels by which the inspiration went to Gujarāt. The Wāsiṭ columns ultimately owe to the Persian *apadāna* columns of the Achaemanian period, such as for example of Persipolis (ca. 5th century B.C.). But the Indian example has to be linked not with ancient Persia but with medieval Middle East with which it had contacts via trade and through the intermediary of Islām itself.³⁰ It is no accident that DhoĪkā minarets possess fluted shaft, and, in any case, a connection with Islāmic culture outside India, particularly that of Middle East, is definitely hinted, even implied we may say. Brown's assertion that "In design these turrets are indigenous, with no definite traces of Islamic influence, but they are apparently an attempt to produce something corresponding to a minaret without, however, any exact knowledge as to what this was like, or for what purpose it was intended" is not, therefore, borne out by facts.

The DhoĪkā minarets, for their basal part just as shaft, simulate, in essential features, a *column* rather than *manār* proper of the Islāmic world, and in this as well as several other respects they stand in a class by themselves, in contrast sharply to all the examples of early minarets that have survived. The almost conical minarets of the Cambay mosque are rather simplified and caricatured version of the Ajmer examples. Those of the Haibat Khān's mosque at Aḥmedābād (ca 1422) are not so actually battered³¹ as the Cambay ones but they still are in the tradition of the tapering type.³² There is a third variety, where the Hindu column of the inornate Mīsraka class has been improvised as minaret, such as for example at the Jāmi Mosque at Māngroḷ in Saurāṣṭra (1364) or the Sayyidi Masjid in the town of Māṅḍal,³³ of the Sultanate period and datable to about the third quarter of the fifteenth century.

The Cambay variety disappears from the subsequent minaret architecture in Gujarāt, poor as it seems in architectural potential. The type such as in Māṅḍal mosque has, likewise, no intrinsic possibility of further development. The DhoĪkā minaret form, combining as it does the prettiness of a Corinthian shaft and the elegance, for its upper part, of a decorative stone lantern in a Japanese garden, possessed, as the later history demonstrates, power of augmenting to size and form monumental. This is proved by the *minārs* of the very first mosque of the Sultanate of Aḥmedābād, namely, the Aḥmed Shāh's mosque founded in 1412³⁴ and next to it, those of the great Jumā Masjid in the selfsame city (1422).³⁵ The substructure in these Sultanate examples is provided by the simulated Hindu shrine sans *śikhara*, and what comes in lieu of *śikhara* is an enlarged, elaborated version of the DhoĪkā minaret. Eight or nine decades separate the DhoĪkā and the Aḥmedābād versions, and what evolutionary changes went in between must

³⁰For details, see Dargahwala.

³¹Burgess, *The Muhammadan*, plate IV.

³²For an early Persian type resembling this one, cf. Masjid Ali Minaret, Isfahan (ca. late 12th century), Hill and Crabar, fig. 516.

³³Burgess, *The Muhammadan Architecture of Ahmedabad*, ASI (WS) Vol. XXIV, pt. II, London 1905, pl. LXXXVI.

³⁴Cf. Henry Cousens, *Somanātha and Other Mediaeval Temples in Kāthiāwād*, ASI (IS), Vol. XLV, Calcutta 1931, pl. LXXXIV; and Burgess, *The Muhammadan*, pt. I, pl. III.

³⁵The upper part of each minaret is lost in earthquake. The drawing of the inner front of the selfsame mosque by James Forbes in 1781 (cf. Burgess, *The Muhammadan*, pt. I, fig. 9) shows them intact and there the flutings in the wall-planes of the drums of the upper section are clearly marked.

account for the few differences and elaborations which distinguish the two. Had the architects in Aḥmedābād, for their *minār* elevation, entirely followed the Hindu conventions, using balaconied stories to increase the height and finish it with a *maṇḍapikā*, pavilion, having a *phāmsanā*, tiered roof, they would have produced structures hardly different from the two contemporaneous Hindu monuments, one Brahmanical and the other Jaina, the famous Kīrttistambha (1459) and the Mānastambha (ca. early 15th century) of Chitor.³⁶ But the placement of the Dholkā type of minaret as a substitution of the *śikhara* at once distinguishes the two, by changing the character of the structure from Hindu to Islāmic.³⁷ Architecturally, the non-tapering verticality of the Dholkā minarets may have been found convenient for grafting it over and blending it with the lower part fashioned after a Hindu shrine form. But there also may be a sentimental reason in choosing this Dholkā variety. For it preserves, it would seem, an imprint on its face of the most ancient architectural devices of Islām, and, with that, the distant but ineffacable association with the homeland of Islām.

³⁶The Mānastambha was formerly regarded as of ca. 1486 by D. R. Bhandarkar and other scholars. But the discovery of the Mahāvīra temple inscription would clearly place it in the earlier part of the fifteenth century. (This being a side issue, I will not elaborate on references. The style of the monument certainly accords with the new dating.) Chitor was known in the medieval times as Citrakūṭa.

³⁷Whether the placement of the *manār* component over the component denoting Hindu shrine was for indicating the triumph of Islām over Hinduism, it is hard to say. The idea possibly is to blend the sacred symbols of the two into a single unity.

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